

A Study on the influence of the self-esteem on the life of the student of Azamgarh district of Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract.

The self-esteem is one's attitudes towards oneself, which may be positive, neutral or negative. It is also called self-evaluation. It has now become a household word. Teachers, parents, therapists, and others have focused efforts on boosting self-esteem, on the assumption that high self-esteem will cause many positive outcome and benefits as assumption that is critically evaluated in this view. High self-esteem is partly the result of good school performance, although high self-esteem does not indicate good school performance as per some report. Job performance in adults is sometimes related to self-esteem. And it is the self-esteem which helps an individual to know their psychological well-being. Occupation success may boost self-esteem rather than reverse.

All together 50 students were selected through simple random sampling from 5 higher secondary schools located at Azamgarh district of Uttar Pradesh, India.

The Rosenberg self-esteem Scale (1965) was employ as a material of the study. The scale consist of 10 items on four point scale with 5 positive and 5 negative with a scale value of 3 strongly agree, 2 agree, 1 disagree and 0 strongly agree for positive items and 0 strongly agree, 1 agree, 2 disagree and 3 strongly agree for the negative items.

Specific statistical techniques like t-test, f-test were used.

Finally, the findings indicated that there was a positive impact of self-esteem on the lives of the students.

Key words: Self-esteem, Academic, Higher Secondary School Students, Psychological Self-Esteem, Occupation.

Introduction

Now-a-days, Self-esteem is a widely used term in social science to reveal a person's own value or worth. Self-esteem is considered to be one of the most important pillars of healthy personality development (Yasemin Erol and Ulrich Orth, 2011). It is the positive and negative evaluation of the identity or an evaluation as well as a perception towards the self. Self-esteem is the evaluation dimension of the self that includes feelings of worthiness, prides and discouragement (Smith & Mackie, 2007). Self-esteem is defined as the experience of being competent to cope with the basic challenges of life and being worthy of happiness (Branden, 1969). It is an attractive psychology construct which can predict certain outcomes which includes even academic achievement.

According to Rosenberg (1965), self-esteem is simply one's attitude towards oneself. He described it as a "favorable or unfavorable attitude towards the self". Various studies have confirmed that self-esteem has a direct relationship with our overall well-being, and we would do well to keep this fact in mind –both for ourselves and for those around us, particularly the development children

we interact with.

Certain characteristics indicate the presence of high or low self-esteem. Characteristic of high self-esteem includes being open to criticism, acknowledging mistakes, being comfortable with giving and receiving compliments, and displaying a harmony between what one says, does, looks, sounds, and moves. People with high self-esteem are unafraid to show their curiosity, discuss their experiences, ideas, and opportunities. They can also enjoy the humorous aspects of their lives and are comfortable with social or personal assertiveness (Branden, 1992).

Review of the literature

Coppersmith (1969) reported that there is no significant difference between the self-esteem of girls and boys.

In a study conducted by Kifer (1973) it was found that successful academic achievement interacted with self-esteem and achievement responsibility as a learner increasing over time. He found that students who had high academic achievement also had a high self-esteem and academic responsibility over time, while unsuccessful academic achievement interacted with self-esteem and academic responsibility as a learner decreasing over time. This finding supports the theory that consistent success or failure was a predictor of self-esteem. The same finding was also reported by Simon and Simon (1975), in which scores on self-esteem were correlated significantly ($r=.33$) with scores on academic achievement tests.

Wylie (1979) in her study concluded that the correlation between self-esteem and students' grade point average was about .30, adding that similar or slightly stronger relationships between self-esteem and scores on various achievement tests.

Redenbach (1991) noted that high self-esteem plays an important role in academic achievement, social and personal responsibility.

Hamachek (1995) reported a positive correlation between self-esteem and academic ability. He concluded that it is vital for educators to be sensitive to student's perceived academic ability. He also indicated that there could be a positive effect on one variable with a positive effect on the other variable (the opposite, negative effect, would also hold true) and that if self-esteem was low, one would see a drop in academic achievement, and if academic achievement was low, one would see a drop in self-esteem.

Butler (1998) examines the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement and noted a relationship between the two with higher academic achievement experienced higher self-esteem.

Abdullah (2000) conducted a study to examine the relationship, inter alia, among a self-esteem and academic performance of university students of a Nigerian University. The purpose was to determine the extent university students' academic performance was influenced by these criterion variables. One thousand, three hundred and thirty five male and female university students from seven faculties participated in the study. They were selected by stratified simple random sampling techniques. Results from multiple regression analysis revealed that clearly the subjective independent variables did not predict objective measures of the students' academic performance. Psycho-sociological evidence indicated that lack of achievement motivation and low self-esteem creates in students lack of interest to strive for high academic performances.

Meftah (2002) studied the relationship, inter alia, between self-esteem and academic achievement of secondary students in Tehran and found that there was a significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement, but no significant difference in self-esteem and academic achievement between girls and boys was noted.

Rubie, Townsend and Moore (2004) emphasized that the best way to improve student achievement is to increase their self-esteem.

Pullmann and Allik (2008) reported that low self-esteem is not essentially an indication of poor academic achievement; nevertheless, it may be a significant predictor of superior school performance.

Akinleke (2012) conducted study on the effect of self-esteem on academic performance, inter alia. Two hundred and fifty randomly drawn final year National Diploma (NDII) students of the

Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, were involved in the study. They were given two questionnaires to be completed between forty to forty five minutes. The study was carried out in a regular class room environment to complete during regular school hours. After collecting information from the students through questionnaires their comprehensive Grade Point Average (GPA) in previous year were also collected. This GPA data were then compared to the scores obtained from the questionnaires. This study discovered that overall, low anxiety students had higher GPAs than high anxiety students and that there is a positive relationship between self-esteem and academic performance. This implication of the findings were that stakeholders in education should formulate policies that help students to cope with anxiety and also initiate programs that will assist the process of learning and mastering challenges as such would result in higher academic achievement.

Hoppe (2013) studied the correlation between self-esteem and education level. The results indicated that there was a significant difference in self-esteem levels between subjects with little and a lot of education with $F(2,42)=6.25, p<.05$.

Mohammad et al. (2015) studied self-esteem and academic achievement among University Students and noted that there exists a strong positive correlation between self-esteem and academic achievement among university students. Further, it was reported that high level of self-esteem leads to good academic performance. Also noted that female students had higher academic performance than male, while male students had high self-esteem than female.

Doodman et al. (2017) studied the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement among high school students in Lamerd city and found a significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement of students at level of 0.01. The findings were consistent with Shafei (1991), Panahi (1998), Coppersmith (1969).

Mirzaei-Alavijeh et al. (2018) studied self-esteem and academic achievement among students of Kermanshah University of Medical Science and reported that planning psychological intervention to increase the level of self-esteem may be useful in promoting academic achievement.

Okafor et al. (2018) studied the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in Imo state and noted that there exists a significant positive relationship between secondary students' self-esteem and their academic achievement.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the self-esteem level among the respondent.
2. To find out the influence of the father's job on the self-esteem of the respondent.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the self-esteem of the boys and the girls.
2. There is no significant difference between the self-esteem of the student with respect to the father's job.

Method

All together 50 student (25 boys & 25 girls) of higher secondary school located at Azamgarh district of Uttar Pradesh, India, where participants of the study. They were selected randomly from 5 schools.

Instrument

Rosenberg self-esteem scale was employed in the collection of data. The questionnaire consists of 10 items on 4-point scale as strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree with a scale value of 4,3,2,1 for positive items and the reverse 1,2,3,4 for negative. Higher scores indicate higher self-esteem. Among the 10 items, item number 1,3,4,7,10 are positive items, while 2,5,6,8,9 negative.

Procedure of data collection

As mentioned above, 50 students participated in the study. The sample was selected in such a manner that 25 boys and 25 girls were randomly selected from different schools located in the Azamgarh district of Uttar Pradesh. Thus the total sample was 50. The 10-item Rosenberg Self-esteem Questionnaire was administered to the students in the class room itself in an environment free from all sorts of disturbances. Instruction was given to the subjects before administration of the questionnaire. They were asked to complete all the items within 15 minutes or as soon as possible. Field editing was carried out to ensure that all the items were completed.

Data Analysis

The correlation between self-esteem of boys and girls was determined on the basis of measurement scores on self-esteem obtained from Rosenberg self-esteem scale. Also the self-esteem of the student is correlated with respect to the job of the father.

Results and Discussion

Table-1: Difference in the level of self-esteem with respect to the sex of the respondent.

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D	t- value	P value	Significant level
Boys	25	1.67	0.488	2.092	0.004	Significant at 0.05 level
Girls	25	2.00	0.378			

The null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, since the value of P=0.004, lies in between 0.001 and 0.005. Also the mean value of boys=1.67 and mean value of girls=2.00 indicates that girls have more self-esteem than that of boys.

Table-2: Difference in the self-esteem of the father with respect to the father's job.

Job Type	Size	Mean	S.D.	F-value	P-value
Farmer	32	2.00	0.00	0.830	0.44
Teacher	11	1.76	0.436		
Business	7	2.00	0.632		

P value=0.44, which is greater than 0.05, indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. The above table clearly indicates that there is no impact on self-esteem of the students with respect to their father job.

Conclusions

Despite of the visible discrimination between the girls and boys within the family itself their self-esteem has been impact the least. Also from the above study it can be concluded that the self-esteem of the girls is more than that of boys. Not only that, there is no impact of father job in respect to the self-esteem of the students.

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